

Democratizing AI: Exploiting Generative AI to Expand Policy Access and Improve Public Participation in Policy-Making in sub-Saharan Africa

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Abstract

- This paper focuses on the potential of Generative AI (GenAI) systems based on Large Language Models (LLMs) to expand citizens' access to government policies and promote public participation in policy-making in sub-Saharan Africa.
- It discusses potential approaches to increase the adoption of GenAI for effective policy dissemination in sub-Saharan Africa
- It also explores strategies to mitigate inequality and uphold fundamental rights and freedoms, such as the right to privacy and personal data protection.

Introduction

- The use of Generative AI (GenAI) tools like ChatGPT, BingChat, and Google Bard is rapidly expanding, and public perception of their impact is still developing.
- Studies have confirmed the potential of GenAI to improve access to information globally.
- Therefore, equitable deployment and effective application of Gen AI solutions can facilitate expanded access to information for citizens, reshape governance, and foster citizen participation in policy-making
- This is particularly important given the challenge of limited access to government policy data and low participation literacy among African citizens.

Research Questions

This research seeks to answer the following questions:

- I. How does GenAI present opportunities for open governance and citizen participation in sub-Saharan Africa?
- II. What are the biggest obstacles and possible solutions to introducing AI in policy-making and governance?
- III. What national strategies and frameworks for AI have been adopted by governments in sub-Saharan Africa and how do they align with global standards?
- IV. What are the challenges and risks posed by AI on governance in Africa and mitigation strategies?

Methodology (1/2)

- This research used a **mixed-method approach for data collection and analysis**.
- Data was collected from **primary and secondary sources** through surveys, mail questionnaires, personal interviews, journals, and existing policy documents.
- There was a **purposive selection of respondents** to ensure that all relevant stakeholders in the industry are assessed including government stakeholders, researchers, members of civil society, and the private sector. This data was used to complement preliminary data collected through surveys and workshops deployed in November 2023 by Policy Vault and its potential impact on data access.
- **Qualitative data collected was analyzed thematically**, with quantitative data used to complement qualitative inputs.

Methodology (2/2)

- **Sampling size and procedure**

Given the scope and objectives of the research, a sample size of approximately 100 respondents across regions of sub-Saharan Africa was selected for this study. The respondents were selected to ensure that all relevant stakeholders in the industry are assessed including government stakeholders, researchers, members of civil society, and the private sector. This data was used to complement data collected through surveys and workshops deployed in November 2023 by Policy Vault on AI and its potential impact on data access.

- **Data collection**

A structured questionnaire was administered to government stakeholders, researchers, AI experts, members of civil society, and the private sector through a Microsoft Form. The questionnaire includes both closed-ended and open-ended questions, allowing for quantitative analysis of responses as well as qualitative insights into participants' perspectives and experiences.

Focus of Key Findings

1 How GenAI presents opportunities for open governance and citizen participation

2 Biggest obstacles and possible solutions to introducing AI in policy-making and governance

3 National strategies, frameworks and infrastructure for AI by governments

4 Challenges and risks posed by AI to African governance

Secondary data sources?

UN trade & development Data
Protection and Privacy
Legislation Worldwide

Oxford Insights
Government AI Readiness
Index 2023

OECD, National
government websites and
Policy Vault

*World Justice
Project Rule of Law
Index 2023*

Who did we interview?

84 participants including
government
officials/employees, AI/ IT
experts, researchers &
NGO representatives

Organizations across the
private and public sector

Sub-Saharan Africa
countries
(Ghana, Nigeria,
Uganda)

4 key takeaways

1 Rwanda stands out as a leader in AI adoption and governance within the sub-Saharan region. It ranks high in the four attributes —open governance, data protection, AI governance, and readiness for AI adoption—as analyzed in this study.

2 Majority believe that regulatory compliance, anti-corruption promotion, and public service delivery are the areas that will benefit the most from the integration of AI and LLMs.

3 Lack of regulatory framework, and ethical concerns are major obstacles to introducing AI in policy-making and governance in Africa.

4 Research participants believe limited technical expertise and capacity among government officials may hinder the effective implementation and oversight of AI technologies in governance processes.

AI Study Landscape

58.3%

have interacted with any GenAI-based platforms or applications designed to facilitate open governance or citizen participation in sub-Saharan Africa

2.2/5

rating was given for the level of technological infrastructure to support AI initiatives for open governance and citizen participation.

64.3%

are extremely and moderately confident that AI (including GenAI) can enhance transparency in governmental processes and citizen participation within sub-Saharan Africa?

45.2%

believe regulatory compliance and anti-corruption areas of governance could benefit most from the integration of AI technologies

1. How GenAI presents opportunities for open governance and citizen participation

Areas of governance that could benefit most from the integration of AI technologies

Fig 1: Perceived benefits of AI and LLMs for governance

Source: Field survey, 2024

As shown in the figure above, the result revealed that 45% of the respondents believe that GenAI can be used to enhance regulatory compliance and promote anti-corruption. For example:

- Generative AI can be used to enhance regulatory compliance by improving the understanding and interpretation of laws and regulations of users of the technology.
- A tool to process and review asset declarations which are currently done manually. It will not only improve efficiency—but also promote transparency in government and increase public awareness of conflicts of interest concerning public officials.

2. Biggest obstacles and possible solutions to introducing AI in policy-making and governance

Obstacles and possible solutions to introducing AI in policy-making and governance

Fig 2: Obstacles arranged in descending order based on their significance by respondents

Source: Field survey, 2024

Possible solutions recommended by respondents

Respondents also provided potential solutions to the obstacles. Some of the major responses to the open-ended questions are classified as follows:

1. Capacity Building:
 - There is a need to train policymakers and government staff in AI technologies to enhance understanding and effective utilization.
 - There is a need to provide employees with guidance and education on how to use generative AI effectively and overcome their fears, challenges, and biases towards this new advanced tool.
2. Regulatory Frameworks:
 - Government must develop clear and robust regulations to ensure ethical use and data privacy.
 - It is very important to ensure high-quality, accessible data and robust privacy protections.
3. Infrastructure Investment:
 - Invest in the necessary technological infrastructure to support AI implementation.
 - Provide incentives for the development of AI integration-based solutions.

3. Analysis of National AI Strategies, Frameworks & Infrastructure

Adoption of National AI Strategies in SSA

- The adoption of an AI regulatory framework in the region is low, with only 10% having developed and launched their national AI strategies.
- So far, only five governments, including Benin, Rwanda, Senegal, Ghana, and Mauritius, have adopted and published their National AI strategies.
- While Kenya, South Africa, and Nigeria are currently in the process of drafting their National AI strategies.

Out of
48 Sub-Saharan African Countries

5 Have adopted a National AI Strategy

Data compiled from Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), national government websites, and Policy Vault repository

Analysis of National Strategies, Frameworks, and Infrastructure for AI in SSA (1/3)

Methodology

Cluster analysis was used to analyze national strategies, frameworks, and infrastructure for AI and citizen participation by governments in sub-Saharan Africa using global standards/indices. The model employed to achieve research objective three was adjusted from the cluster analysis model used by James, Gregory & Kevin (2023) to analyze different countries' national AI strategies (excluding African countries) by categorizing their inclusion of different attributes as either High, Medium, or Low.

Attributes

- 1. Open governance:** measures the extent to which a government shares information, empowers people with tools to hold the government accountable, and fosters citizen participation in public policy deliberations (*Data source: WJP Rule of Law Index 2023*)
- 2. Data protection:** the level at which countries adopt data protection and privacy legislation (*Data source: UNCTAD*)
- 3. AI governance:** the level at which countries adopt national AI strategy and legislation (*Data source: OECD, National government websites and Policy Vault*)
- 4. Readiness for AI adoption:** ranking of countries based on 3 pillars: Government, Technology Sector, and Data & Infrastructure (*Data source: Oxford Insights Government AI Readiness Index 2023*)

Analysis of National Strategies, Frameworks, and Infrastructure for AI in SSA (2/3)

Sub-Saharan African countries clustered as either High, Medium, or Low based on four attributes including the level of openness, data protection, AI governance, and readiness for AI adoption. The chart shows the **number of countries** for each cluster across the four attributes.

Fig 4: Cluster analysis of National strategies, frameworks, and infrastructure for AI in Sub-Saharan Africa

65%

of sub-Saharan African countries **have a data protection policy**

Only **3**

Of 48 sub-Saharan African countries **fall under the high cluster for government readiness for AI adoption** based on assessment of Government, Technology Sector, and Data & Infrastructure

Source: Data compiled from Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), national government websites, and Policy Vault repository

Analysis of National Strategies, Frameworks, and Infrastructure for AI in SSA (3/3)

Cluster	Low	Medium	High
Open Governance <i>(score 0-1)</i>	<u>0 - 0.24 (14 countries)</u> Cabo Verde, Chad, Equatorial Guinea, Lesotho, Sao Tome and Principe, Eswatini, Seychelles, Comoros, Somalia, South Sudan, Guinea-Bissau, Burundi, CAR, Eritrea.	<u>0.25 - 0.49 (28 countries)</u> Burkina Faso, Botswana, Liberia, Malawi, Mali, Madagascar, Senegal, Nigeria, Zambia, Angola, Uganda, Tanzania, Sierra Leone, Gambia, Benin, Gabon, Niger, Guinea, Mozambique, Cote d'Ivoire, Sudan, DRC, Zimbabwe, Congo, Cameroon, Togo, Ethiopia, Mauritania (28 countries)	<u>≥0.5 (6 countries)</u> South Africa, Namibia, Rwanda, Mauritius, Ghana, Kenya (6 countries)
Data protection <i>(Availability of data protection laws)</i>	<u>With no legislation/no data (11 countries)</u> Comoros, Somalia, South Sudan, Mozambique, Congo, Sudan, Mauritania, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Guinea-Bissau, Burundi, CAR, Eritrea	<u>With draft legislation (6 countries)</u> Namibia, Ethiopia, Tanzania, Eswatini, Malawi, Seychelles	<u>With legislation (31 countries)</u> Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Chad, Cote D'Ivoire, Nigeria, DRC, Gambia, Gabon, Equatorial Guinea, Guinea, South Africa, Kenya, Ghana, Namibia, Mali, Senegal, Lesotho, Madagascar, Mauritania, Mauritius, Niger, Rwanda, Sao Tome and Principe, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe (31)
AI Governance <i>(Availability of national AI strategy)</i>	<u>With no legislation/no data (11 countries)</u> Angola, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Chad, Cote D'Ivoire, DRC, Gambia, Gabon, Equatorial Guinea, Guinea, Namibia, Mali, Lesotho, Madagascar, Mauritania, Sao Tome and Principe, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Ethiopia, Tanzania, Eswatini, Malawi, Seychelles, Comoros, Somalia, South Sudan, Mozambique, Congo, Sudan, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Guinea-Bissau, Burundi, CAR, Eritrea, Niger.	<u>With draft AI policy or regulatory agencies (6 countries)</u> Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa	<u>With legislation (5 countries)</u> Senegal, Rwanda, Benin, Mauritius, Ghana
Readiness for AI Adoption <i>(Score 100 with average score for SSA at 30%)</i>	<u>0-25 (15 countries)</u> South Sudan, Eritrea, CAR, Burundi, DRC, Somalia, Liberia, Comoros, Chad, Guinea-Bissau, Congo, Sudan, Niger, Sierra Leone, Malawi (15 countries)	<u>26-44 (30 countries)</u> Mozambique, Lesotho, Sao Tome and Principe, Eswatini, Mauritania, Guinea, Mali, Burkina Faso, Equatorial Guinea, Madagascar, Angola, Togo, Gambia, Cameroon, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Ghana, Ethiopia, Cote d'Ivoire, Tanzania, Gabon, Uganda, Namibia, Cabo Verde, Seychelles, Botswana, Nigeria, Kenya, Benin, Senegal.	<u>>45 (3 countries)</u> Mauritius, South Africa, Rwanda (3 countries)

4. Challenges and risks posed by AI to African governance

Challenges and Risks of AI on Governance in Africa

Fig 5: challenges and risks arranged in descending order based on agreement by respondents

Source: Field survey, 2024

Key Findings –in summary

<p>1. Opportunities for open governance and citizen participation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• AI and LLMs present an opportunity to enhance regulatory compliance and improve anti-corruption activities in Africa.• It can serve as a tool for expanding policy access on the continent.• It can also be deployed to improve public participation e.g. quick sorting and analysis of citizens' thoughts and comments on a policy matter during and immediately after public consultations.
<p>2. Obstacles and possible solutions to introducing AI in policy-making and governance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lack of robust regulatory framework hinders full adoption of AI for policy-making and governance in Africa.
<p>3. Analysis of National AI Strategies, Frameworks & Infrastructure</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. So far, only five governments (representing 10% of SSA), including Benin, Rwanda, Senegal, Ghana, and Mauritius, have adopted and published their National AI strategies2. Examining the clusters based on the four attributes, it becomes evident that Rwanda stands out as a leader in AI adoption and governance within the sub-Sahara region. It ranks high in the four attributes — open governance, data protection, AI governance, and readiness for AI adoption—as analyzed in this study. South Africa and Mauritius also demonstrate strong performance, appearing in high clusters across three attributes.
<p>Recommendations</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Ethical concerns can be addressed by establishing clear and comprehensive regulations for AI development and deployment.2. Deliberate measures and speedy action should be deployed to correct any observed bias.3. Government agencies should adopt AI as a tool to complement traditional methods of service delivery for efficiency and cost reduction.4. Government should support capacity-building programs to train government officials, policymakers, and stakeholders on AI technologies and their implications to enhance informed decision-making.

Thank You

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